

PATHYA AND APATHYA IN PRAMEH: AN AYURVEDIC PERSPECTIVE**Dr. Monali Rajkumar Gore*¹, Dr. Abhijeet Ashok Borude²,****Dr. Sandeep Thaknath Shinde³**¹PG Scholar Dept. of Kayachikitsa, PMT's Ayurvedic Medical College, Shevgaon.²Reader Dept. of Kayachikitsa, PMT's Ayurvedic Medical College, Shevgaon.³Hod Dept. of Kayachikitsa, PMT's Ayurvedic Medical College, Shevgaon.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19874404>***Corresponding Author****Dr. Monali Rajkumar Gore**PG Scholar Dept. of Kayachikitsa,
PMT's Ayurvedic Medical College,
Shevgaon.**How to cite this Article** Dr. Monali Rajkumar Gore*¹, Dr. Abhijeet Ashok Borude², Dr. Sandeep Thaknath Shinde³ (2026). Pathya And Apathya In Prameh: An Ayurvedic Perspective. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(9), 172-179.

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ABSTRACT

Effective management of any disease requires proper understanding of its etiology, pathogenesis, and suitable therapeutic planning. In Ayurveda, special importance is given to Pathya (wholesome diet and lifestyle) and Apathya (unwholesome diet and habits) as essential components of treatment.^[4] Prameha is one such disorder in which dietary regulation and lifestyle modification significantly influence disease progression and prognosis.^[5] Classical Ayurvedic texts such as Charaka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita, Ashtanga Hridaya, and Ashtanga Sangraha provide detailed descriptions of the causes, pathogenesis, and clinical features of Prameha.^[4-6] According to Ayurveda, Prameha is categorized as a Santarpanajanya Vyadhi, which develops due to excessive nourishment and sedentary habits.^[4] Among its various forms,

Madhumeha closely resembles Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus described in modern medicine.^[6]Type-2 diabetes is characterized by insulin resistance and usually occurs in middle-aged individuals.^[7] Proper adherence to Pathya and avoidance of Apathya play a major role in controlling blood glucose levels and preventing complications.^[8]**KEYWORDS:** Prameh, Pathya, Apathya.**INTRODUCTION**In recent decades, lifestyle disorders have increased significantly across the world. Among these conditions, Diabetes Mellitus has become a major global health concern.^[7] It is a

metabolic disorder characterized by persistent hyperglycemia and glycosuria due to abnormalities in insulin secretion, insulin action, or both.^[8] According to the World Health Organization, millions of people worldwide are affected by diabetes, and the number continues to rise steadily.^[8]

Rapid urbanization, unhealthy dietary habits, reduced physical activity, and increased stress have contributed significantly to the growing prevalence of diabetes.^[7] India is considered one of the countries with a large number of diabetic patients, which has led to its recognition as the “Diabetes Capital” in recent times.^[8]

In Ayurveda, diabetes is described under the broad term Prameha. The term Prameha is derived from the Sanskrit root “*Mih*”, which means to pass urine. The prefix “*Pra*” indicates excessiveness, implying frequent and excessive urination, which is a characteristic feature of the disease.^[3]

Ayurvedic classics classify Prameha into twenty types, based on the predominance of Doshas.

- 10 types due to Kapha
- 6 types due to Pitta
- 4 types due to Vata.^[4,6]

Among these, Madhumeha represents the advanced stage and is comparable to diabetes mellitus described in modern medicine.^[8]

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

1. To review the concept of Prameha as described in classical Ayurvedic literature.
2. To collect and analyze references related to Pathya and Apathya in the management of Prameha.
3. To highlight the role of dietary and lifestyle modifications in controlling Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present review is based on information collected from classical Ayurvedic texts including Charaka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita, Ashtanga Hridaya, and Ashtanga Sangraha,^[4-7] along with other Ayurvedic references related to Pathya-Apathya. Modern medical literature and research articles were also reviewed using databases such as PubMed, Google Scholar, and other scientific search platforms.^[6,7]

Etiology (Nidana) of Prameha

Ayurveda describes two major categories of etiological factors responsible for the development of Prameha.

1. Sahaja Prameha

2. Apathya Nimittaja Prameha^[4]

This type of Prameha develops due to improper diet and unhealthy lifestyle practices.

Common dietary causes mentioned in classical texts include.

- Excessive consumption of curd
- Frequent intake of meat from domestic or aquatic animals
- Excess use of milk and dairy products
- Consumption of newly harvested grains
- Excessive intake of jaggery and sweet preparations
- Diets that aggravate Kapha Dosha.^[3,4]

According to Acharya Sushruta, the intake of cold, oily, sweet, and fatty foods, along with excessive liquid consumption, contributes to the development of Prameha.^[5]

Purva Roopa

Acharya Vagbhat described that person those having

bad body odor,

flaccidity of body parts,

desire for comfort in the bed,
sitting down and sleep,
thickening of the heart, eyes, tongue, and ears,
stoutness of the body,
greater increase of hairs and nails,
desire for cold,
dryness of the throat and palate,
sweet taste in the mouth,
burning sensation of palms and soles,
swarming of ants towards his urine are the prodromal features of Prameha.

As per Acharya Charka Prameha aggravated Tridoshas develop following characteristic in prediabetic stage. These characters are

Malin danta (accumulation of waste over teeth),
Hastapad daha (burning sensation in hands and feet),
Mukhamadhurya (oral sweetness),
Sweda (sweating),
Shithilangata (flaccidity of body),
excessive growth of hair, nails etc.,
matting of hair,
Trishna (thirst),
fleshy smell from body,
adherence of excreta in body orifices,
accumulation of bees and ants over the body and urine.^[20]

Prameha Roopam

The clinical features of Prameha grouped under two categories 1) Mutra Sambandhi

Lakshanas - Prabhuta mutrata (more frequent urination), Avil mootrata (turbid urination).

2) Sarvadaihika Lakshanas

a. Apathyanimittaja: Person having Prameha due to Apathyanimittaja (excessive consumption of food, oily skin, wants to sit on comfortable chair or sleep.

b. Sahaja: Person having Sahaj type of Prameha will be lean and thin, having dryness in the body, less intake of diet and feeling of excessive thirst.

Lifestyle Factors (Vihara Hetu)

Several lifestyle practices can increase the risk of Prameha:

- Excessive sleeping
- Daytime sleeping (Diwaswapna)
- Lack of physical exercise
- Sedentary habits
- Laziness and inactivity
- Avoidance of detoxification therapies

These factors lead to the aggravation of **Kapha Dosha and Meda Dhatu**, which ultimately results in the development of Prameha.

Role of Pathya–Apathya in Management

Ayurveda places great emphasis on **dietary regulation and lifestyle discipline** for maintaining health and preventing disease.

Pathya refers to wholesome food and habits that support the proper functioning of body channels (*Srotas*). According to Ayurvedic principles, proper Pathya itself can act as a therapeutic measure.

On the other hand, **Apathya** includes unwholesome foods and habits that disturb the balance of Doshas and contribute to disease progression.

In the management of Prameha, adherence to Pathya helps to.

- Maintain normal blood glucose levels
- Improve metabolism
- Reduce excessive body weight
- Prevent complications associated with diabetes.^[7]

Classical Pathya–Apathya for Prameha

(Based on Charaka Samhita & Sushruta Samhita)^[4,5]

Prameha (comparable to Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus) is mainly caused by **Kapha and Meda aggravation**. Therefore, foods and habits that reduce **Kapha and Meda** are recommended, while Kapha-increasing substances should be avoided.

Table: Pathya–Apathya in Prameha.

Category	Pathya (Recommended)	Apathya (To Be Avoided)
Cereals (Dhanya)	Yava (Barley), Godhuma (old wheat), Kodrava, Shyamaka	Navanna (newly harvested grains), excessive rice
Pulses (Shimbi Dhanya)	Mudga (green gram), Chanaka (chickpea), Kulattha (horse gram)	Masha (black gram), heavy pulse preparations
Vegetables (Shaka)	Karela (bitter gourd), Patola (pointed gourd), Karavellaka, leafy vegetables	Potato, yam, sweet vegetables
Fruits (Phala)	Jamun, Amalaki, Kapittha, pomegranate	Banana, mango, grapes, sweet fruits
Dairy Products	Takra (buttermilk)	Curd (Dadhi), excessive milk, cream
Sweeteners	Honey (Madhu) in small quantity	Sugar, jaggery, sweets
Meat (Mamsa)	Lean meat of animals from dry land (Jangala Mamsa)	Fatty meat, aquatic animal meat
Oils and Fats	Mustard oil, small quantity of ghee	Excess oil, fried food
Drinks	Warm water, herbal decoctions	Sweet beverages, alcohol
Lifestyle (Vihara)	Regular exercise, walking, physical activity	Sedentary lifestyle
Sleep	Proper night sleep	Daytime sleeping (Diwaswapna)
Mental habits	Discipline, controlled diet	Laziness, overindulgence

Important Pathya Foods Mentioned in Classical Texts

According to **Acharya Charaka** and **Acharya Sushruta**, the following foods are especially beneficial for Prameha patients.

- **Yava (Barley)** – helps reduce Kapha and Meda
- **Kulattha (Horse gram)** – improves metabolism
- **Mudga (Green gram)** – light and easy to digest
- **Takra (Buttermilk)** – improves digestion
- **Madhu (Honey)** – helps in reducing fat accumulation

Importance of Yava in Prameha vyadhi

Yava (barley) has prime importance in the Pathya of Prameha in all the Ayurveda classics. It is mentioned that the diet of Pramehi should consist of Yava predominantly in the forms of Satu (Glumous), chapati etc. Yava is the annual cereal grain crop that is consumed as a major food and as a feed for animals. It is considered as fourth most important crop in the world after wheat, maize and rice.

Prameha patient should take various edible preparations of Yava mixed with honey like Mantha, Churna, Odana etc. Along with water the Roasted Yava powder should be mixed and

taken for 1 month which cures Prameha. Powder of Yava should be kept overnight in Triphala kashaya and should be taken next day morning along with purana Madhu (Madhu which is 12 months old should be used preferably). Roasted Yava cures all types of Prameha. Various preparation of the barley or bamboo seed or wheat firstly eaten by asses, horses, cows, swans & deer & then collected from their dung should be given to the patients suffering from Prameha.

Rasa	Madhura, Anurasa-Kashaya
Guna	Ruksha, Aguru, Mridu
Veerya	Sheeta
Vipaka	Katu
Karma	Kapha- Pitta hara Lekhana, Medohar, Krimahar, balya
Roga	Prameha, Stholya etc

CONCLUSION

Prameha is a metabolic disorder described extensively in Ayurvedic literature and is closely comparable to Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus in modern medicine. Improper dietary habits and sedentary lifestyle are major contributing factors in the development of this condition. Ayurveda places great emphasis on the importance of Pathya and Apathya in disease management. Proper adherence to wholesome diet and healthy lifestyle practices can significantly help in controlling blood glucose levels and preventing disease progression. Therefore, integration of Ayurvedic principles of Pathya-Apathya with modern medical management may provide a holistic approach for the effective control of diabetes.

DISCUSSION

The increasing prevalence of diabetes worldwide highlights the need for effective preventive strategies. Modern medicine primarily focuses on pharmacological treatment to control blood glucose levels. However, lifestyle modification remains a fundamental aspect of diabetes management.

Ayurveda emphasizes the concept of prevention and health maintenance through proper diet and lifestyle practices. The principles of Pathya-Apathya described in classical texts align closely with modern recommendations for diabetes management, which include dietary control, weight management, and regular physical activity.

The Ayurvedic approach focuses on correcting the underlying metabolic imbalance rather than merely controlling symptoms. By regulating diet and lifestyle, it is possible to reduce the severity of the disease and prevent complications.

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